

MAIN ISSUES IN THE SPHERE OF INTERNATIONAL LEGAL REGULATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: The article is devoted to an overview of key issues related to the legal regulation of artificial intelligence. The author notes that there are no unified positions regarding the legal regulation of AI. One group of scientists considers the legal regulation of AI necessary, while others warn that excessive regulation may hinder the development of AI. The article highlights the following key issues: the content of the concept of "artificial intelligence" (AI), the legal personality of AI, i.e. the issue of recognizing AI as a subject of law, the liability of AI in the event of harm. The author notes that at the moment there are many definitions of AI, the issue of recognizing AI as a subject has not been resolved unambiguously, however, the so-called theory of fictitious legal personality of artificial intelligence prevails, which assumes giving the legal status of AI certain features inherent in the status of legal entities. The article provides examples of legal regulations in the EU, as well as examples of cases from judicial practice on the recognition of AI as a subject of law.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, electronic person, legal personality of AI, fictitious legal personality of AI, liability of AI.

At the moment, many different acts devoted to AI ethics have been adopted around the world within the framework of international organizations and in individual countries. In order to ensure clear legal regulation of activities in the field of AI, it is initially necessary to define the legal content of the term "artificial intelligence" itself, as well as to identify its basic features. Despite the intensive development of AI and the dynamic development of scientific debate in this area, there are still no unified approaches to defining AI. One reason for the lack of a unified definition of the concept of "artificial intelligence" is the interdisciplinary nature of approaches to understanding this issue, since the implementation of scientific research in the field of artificial intelligence requires the unification of knowledge from various scientific fields. [5]. In other words, the definition of artificial intelligence depends on the discipline in which the phenomenon is considered.

One of the definitions was proposed by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG) of the European Commission within the European Union in a report presented on April 8, 2019 [8]. In this document, the Group distinguishes between the concepts of artificial intelligence systems as such and artificial intelligence as a scientific discipline. Artificial intelligence systems are defined in the report as "systems that exhibit intelligent behaviour by analysing their environment and taking actions — with a certain degree of autonomy — to achieve specific goals." There are many other options for defining the concept of "artificial intelligence", however, there is no generally accepted definition enshrined in an international legal document. At the same time, it is possible to note the similarity of researchers' opinions regarding the basic characteristics of artificial intelligence, in particular, that systems based on artificial intelligence are systems that make critical decisions without human participation.

The European Parliament resolution "Civil Law Rules on Robotics" of 17 February 2017 notes the need to develop common concepts for such terms as "cyber-physical systems", "intelligent autonomous robots" taking into account the following features:

- 1) the ability to be autonomous and exchange data; 2) the ability to learn from experience;
- 3) the presence of minimal physical support;
- 4) the ability to adapt to the external environment;
- 5) the absence of life [2, C.26].

It is important to emphasize that to date, no official document contains a normative definition of the concept of "artificial intelligence", although the term itself is actively used in many countries, along with such terms as "robots". Thus, modern science has not developed a uniform understanding of artificial intelligence. Today we can talk about many definitions of artificial intelligence, since the areas of its application are very wide.

The above raises the question of determining the content of the concept of "artificial intelligence" and its recording in legal texts. The lack of a clear legal definition of artificial intelligence hinders the resolution of other legal issues, in particular such issues as the legal personality of artificial intelligence, liability for harm caused by the use of artificial intelligence. Thus, the military use of artificial intelligence violates the most basic natural and inalienable human right - the right to life. Currently, artificial intelligence is developing in almost all areas of activity of the armed forces of many states.

Another example - the implantation of cyber-physical systems into the human body is already becoming a reality today. The European Parliament, in its report of 27.01.2017 with recommendations to the European Commission on the civil-law regulation of robotics, draws attention to the risk associated with the possibility of hacking or disabling operational programming systems embedded in the human body, or erasing their memory, which can endanger human health, and in special cases even their life..[4, C.70].

AI poses a threat to human rights. Another example is the use of artificial intelligence units in public administration, which initially undermines the idea of governing people by people based on democratic procedures and principles. In addition, artificial intelligence units can be successfully used in the judicial process, including for the analysis of judicial practice and the substantiation of judicial decisions. This can simultaneously lead to a violation of the right of citizens to a fair trial. Acceleration of the consideration of court cases in such a case does not always lead to the humanization of judicial activity and compliance with the principle of justice. [4, C.72]. In addition, the use of artificial intelligence technologies allows for open interference in private life, nullifying this recently won right of people. [4, C.75].

In this regard, a set of issues regarding the legal regulation of AI has been formed to date.

The first issue is the debate about the possibility of recognizing/not recognizing artificial intelligence as a person. A number of researchers believe that the legal status of an electronic system with elements of artificial intelligence and a perfect autonomous unit cannot be the same. The latter, in their opinion, can be recognized without unnecessary hesitation as a full-fledged cyber subject of society, but with the proviso that such a status will have different options in terms of the range of rights and responsibilities, since it is not possible to put an ATM, a smart home system and a combat robot in the same row. From this, they conclude that systems with artificial intelligence must have a certain legal status, which will depend on the functionality and other features of a particular system. [1].

When discussing the issue of the possibility of recognizing artificial intelligence as a subject of law, two options are put forward. In the first case, artificial intelligence is understood only as a technical means with the legal regime of a thing. In the second case, it is recognized as an electronic person by analogy with a legal entity through the use of a legal fiction. Both options are not fully adequate.

The qualification of artificial intelligence as an object of law does not take into account the ability to think and make independent decisions. In the second case, artificial intelligence is equated with a person similar to a human. The model of legal regulation depends on the solution to this issue, starting with the possibility of entering into legal relations and up to imposing legal liability on such intelligence.

At the same time, it is obvious that for artificial intelligence to acquire the status of a subject of law, it must have such a quality as will. Artificial intelligence does not have volitional ability. Therefore, granting legal personality to artificial intelligence will in any case be a fiction [2, C.26]. The most stable and progressively developed in scientific works is the theory of fictitious legal capacity of artificial intelligence, which assumes that the legal status of AI will be given certain features inherent in the status of legal entities.

As a result of this controversy, the use of the term "electronic person" was proposed, and the idea of endowing it with legal capacity is increasingly heard in the European Union. The draft report on the status of the "electronic person" developed by the European Parliament Committee on Legal Affairs indicates such signs of "intelligence" of robots as the ability to analyze data; the ability to adapt their behavior; the presence of physical support; autonomy acquired through sensors and contact with the environment, as well as the ability to self-learn. The document notes that the most highly developed and high-tech robots should acquire the status of an electronic person with its inherent legal capacity, and this status should always be used when robots independently make volitional decisions or otherwise interact with third parties. Such approaches directly indicate the desire of a part of society to consider the "electronic person" as a real actor, since it is assigned this or that duty, which it can fulfill or not. In this regard, the question arises: who will be responsible for failure to fulfill this duty? And there is no unambiguous position here. At the same time, there are other points of view on this issue. Thus, the American professor L. Soulum has already formulated theses proving the legal groundlessness of recognizing that artificial intelligence has the status of a person. He believes that electronic systems, and even systems with full artificial intelligence, cannot be considered as entities similar or identical to people. And as an example, he cites the 14th Amendment to the US Constitution, according to which all persons born or naturalized in the United States, being subjects of the jurisdiction of such, are citizens of the United States. Thus, only people can be born, therefore, artificial intelligence cannot have the rights of citizens [6, C.96].

The second question is a question that follows from the question of recognizing AI as a subject - the problem of liability for harm caused by such intelligence. In legal literature, various models of imposing tort liability are discussed:

- on the owner of the rights to a device equipped with artificial intelligence;
- on the software developer;
- on the operator servicing artificial intelligence [2, C.26].

Currently, one of the pressing issues, which has both theoretical and practical significance, is the possibility of recognizing robotics as a subject of law. Obviously, today it is difficult to underestimate scientific and technological progress, which marked the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) and other technologies. In this regard, the possibility of recognizing a robot with artificial intelligence as a subject of law, legislative consolidation of its legal status, as well as the consequences of the development of robotics are discussed. The existence of the need to recognize artificial intelligence as a subject of law is a debatable issue. The possibility of assigning a robot the status of a legal entity is a rather controversial issue.

Most lawyers believe that the robot should be given the status of an "electronic person". Since it is an object of increased danger, it must have an operator - a "guardian" (the owner of this robot), who will be responsible for the actions of the work, but the robot will have a number of rights.

Without an operator, the robot will not be able to perform a number of certain significant actions. Artificial intelligence operates on the basis of self-learning, i.e. the operator, in turn, will be able to contribute to the behavior of the robot. Not every robot will fit these rules, for example, an exception may be a robot vacuum cleaner, which simply performs the function of cleaning floors. Each robot will have to be registered under a certain identification number.

Failure to register a robot may entail both administrative and criminal punishment. Criminal punishment may be applied only if this robot contradicts the principles of humanism, morality, etc. Registration cannot be made if the robot does not have certain functions, namely: an emergency shutdown button, an action cancellation mode, etc. In this case, the operator will have to pass a special commission for access to ownership of such a robot in order to somehow exclude the fact that the robot will be used to create conditions for committing actions prohibited by law. In order to avoid the emergence of any autonomous

combat system that can kill on its own initiative, AI must necessarily be guided by certain rules that cannot be replaced by interference in the system.

Case law on AI issues is gradually developing, in particular cases on recognizing AI as legal entities. For example, the DABUS case in the USA. Dr. Steven Thaler created a device called DABUS, which consists of neural networks and was used to invent an emergency warning light, a food container that improves grip and heat transfer, and much more. Thaler believes that artificial intelligences should be patent holders and has launched numerous lawsuits in at least 15 countries to prove his case. The US Court of Appeal once again confirmed previous decisions that artificial intelligence cannot have invention patents. So far, all cases in the UK, US, and New Zealand have been lost. In Australia, Ryan Abbott, a professor at the University of Surrey, filed patent applications on behalf of Thaler. In August 2021, the Federal Court of Australia ruled that AI systems can be recognized as inventors. However, in April 2022, this decision was overturned. The main argument of the courts is that no AI creates a new invention on its own, it is a tool that ultimately acts on human instructions. However, Thaler and Abbott are not giving up and continue to appeal the decisions. In connection with the latest refusal, Thaler asks for a re-hearing at the Federal Circuit level. The current position on this issue is as follows: at the current stage of legal development, the illegal behavior of artificial intelligence must always result in human responsibility. Thus, the PACE recommendations “Merging with Technology, Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights” of April 28, 2017 No. 2102 also explicitly state that responsibility for the actions of artificial intelligence lies with a person regardless of the circumstances of the incident, and even references to the independence of decisions made by artificial intelligence units cannot exempt their creators, owners and operators from liability. Such decisions are a natural consequence of the doctrinal approach to the mass adoption of artificial intelligence systems and their assimilation into everyday life, which is being tested in modern conditions.

In this context, the role of international law may consist in coordinating the development of legal regulation; possibly in developing internationally agreed guidelines to ensure the integration of fundamental values in the development of autonomous systems using artificial intelligence; in adapting existing norms and concepts; in filling gaps in legal regulation; in developing and adopting the concept of responsibility [7].

Without questioning the need for legal regulation of these technologies, the scientific community is debating the scale of such regulation. In particular,

whether it is worth limiting ourselves to modernizing current legislative acts (and perhaps their broad interpretation) or whether it is necessary to introduce a new branch of legislation for this area. Representatives of the first approach point to the need to avoid a situation of excessive regulation of technologies that hinders their development. As an example, they refer to the history of the formation of the Internet, the lack of regulation of which allowed it to fully develop its potential (although it is worth noting that the history of the Internet has apparently approached a point beyond which its development free from regulation becomes impossible due to the clash of interests of transnational technology corporations and states). Representatives of the opposite approach justify their position by the specifics of artificial intelligence systems, which require the adoption of new legislation. [3].

Thus, artificial intelligence-based technologies are already an integral part of modern life, but the legal regulation of such developments still remains an open question. It is no exaggeration to say that legal systems are currently hopelessly behind the development of artificial intelligence technology. There is no universal approach to the legal regulation of this problem, which is explained by the conciliatory nature of international law, which dictates a slow and painstaking process of decision-making and the creation of legal norms, which is also reinforced by the divergence of interests of subjects of international law, especially states. This is reflected at the national level of legal regulation. Despite the relevance of existing and potential problems associated with activities in the field of artificial intelligence, international norms, as well as the legislation of individual states, currently do not have the necessary tools and mechanisms to cope with the threats and risks posed.

References:

1. Берггольц В. Правовой статус и разграничение ответственности при разработке и использовании инструментов искусственного интеллекта // International Journal of Humanities and Natural Sciences, vol. 6-3 (45), 2020. – С.23-27.
2. Васильев А. Искусственный интеллект: правовые основы. //Известия АлтГУ. Юридические науки. 2018. №6 (104) – С.23-26.
3. Казанцев Д. Анализ тенденций становления правового регулирования искусственного интеллекта и роботов // Научные записки молодых исследователей № 1/2022. - С.66-76.
4. Кашкин С. , Покровский А. Искусственный интеллект, робототехника и защита прав человека в ЕС. // Вестник Университета им. Кутафина. №4/2019. – С.64-90.

5. Латипова А. Искусственный интеллект и международное право. <https://inter-legal.ru/iskusstvennyj-intellekt-i-mezhdunarodnoe-pravo>
6. Понкин И.В., Редькина А.И. Искусственный интеллект с точки зрения права. //Вестник РУДН. Серия: Юридические науки 2018 Т. 22. № 1. – С.91-109.
7. Шестак В.А., Волеводз А.Г. Современные потребности правового обеспечения искусственного интеллекта: взгляд из России// Russian Journal of Criminology, 2019, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 197–206/ Всероссийский криминологический журнал. 2019. Т. 13, № 2. С. 197–206.
8. High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence. (2019). A definition of AI: Main capabilities and scientific disciplines. European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=56341

